

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-3-221-IG-1% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	7	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 3 221
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	270.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 270.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/14/2022 11:38:36 AM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 9:41:36 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	10.883	202350	50.63	6889
2	12.999	197319	49.37	6427

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-3-210-IG-1% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20221014
Vial:	7	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	3
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	270.0nm
Run Time:	17.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 270.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/14/2022 3:10:11 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 9:43:54 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	10.520	18795534	98.41	673046
2	12.763	304406	1.59	10692